

TEACHING VOCABULARY IN ADVANCED GROUPS

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Abstract: This article illustrates how to teach upper-intermediate and advanced students. In spite of this, several methods and activities are given which are useful and essential while teachers educate vocabulary to students.

Keywords: ELT classroom, synonyms and antonyms, receptive-productive gap, rationale of the lesson, group work.

Within the title of this article I have isolated educating and learning – why? Well, when it comes to lexicon I think that a few exercises are outlined for displaying and honing lexicon, whereas other activities are outlined to assist understudies record and actuate lexicon. Of course, it's not a clear isolate and numerous exercises cover both regions, but I do think it is an critical qualification to form.

Subsequently, I am attending to separate this article into two wide segments: the primary looking at diverse strategies and exercises planned to educate lexicon, both modern and ancient (or commonplace); and strategies and activities that center on learning lexicon. These afterward procedures and exercises do have to be presented (or instructed) to the understudies, but once they have aced them, they can be utilized freely of the educator.

In this area we'll see at different procedures for displaying and, to a lesser degree, honing lexicon. It is imperative to realize that a great instructor will not depend on fair one of these methods, but will utilize a combination. Distinctive procedures are suitable for diverse lexicon things conjointly for diverse sorts of learner. As you studied through the distinctive strategies, attempt to think what

words would be best instructed utilizing the procedure and for which words the strategy would likely not work exceptionally well.

Advanced learners can for the most part communicate well, having learnt all the fundamental structures of the language. In any case, they have to be broaden their lexicon to specific themselves more clearly and suitably in a wide extend of circumstances.

Students might indeed have a responsive information of a more extensive run of lexicon, which suggests they can perceive the thing and perceive its meaning. By the by, their beneficial utilize of a wide extend of vocabulary is normally constrained, and this is often one of the ranges that require more prominent consideration. At this organize we are concerned not as it were with students understanding the meaning of words, but too being able to use them fittingly, taking into consideration components such as oral or written utilize of the language; degree of formality, style and others, which we are getting to detail in Part 2.

Instructing lexicon to progressed learners has its possess particular set of challenges and the approaches we utilize effectively with lower-level classes are not continuously suitable for upper-intermediate and progressed bunches. Here are four components it's worth taking into consideration in the event that you're planning a lexicon action for a better level class:

1. Choosing which words to teach

When you start learning a language, it makes sense to learn the most frequently used words first. For learners up to around intermediate level, focusing on the most frequent 2,000-3,000 words in English gives them a core operating vocabulary and enables them to communicate most basic concepts. This core vocabulary can be found in word lists such as the Oxford 3000 and provides an obvious basis for a vocabulary syllabus up to around B1+ level (click here to read my previous blog post about the Oxford 3000). Beyond those basics though, deciding which words to focus on becomes more difficult. There are over a quarter of a million words in English and a scattergun approach that just picks out 'interesting' new words from reading texts or selects lists of synonyms around a topic isn't necessarily the most

effective. Building an advanced vocabulary requires a balance of lexis that's relevant to the individual students' needs and a stock of general-purpose mid-frequency vocabulary. [1]

2. Narrowing the receptive-productive gap

At lower levels, new vocabulary typically moves quite quickly from a learner's receptive vocabulary (words they understand) to their productive vocabulary (words they use themselves) simply because they need those basic words and expressions to communicate; they fill a semantic gap. As vocabulary moves beyond the basics though and starts to express subtler nuances of meaning, it becomes easier to avoid using. Take the verb *lack*, for instance, it will probably be familiar to most learners by about B1 level and they won't have trouble understanding a sentence like: [2]

The players lack confidence.

In communicating the same thought themselves, in any case, a learner is more likely to drop back on less complex, more commonplace vocabulary:

The players aren't very confident.

Thus whereas a learner's open lexicon may proceed to develop, their beneficial lexicon regularly doesn't keep pace as they discover they can get by with attempted and tried words and expressions. Narrowing this ever-widening hole includes a conscious effort and an component of risk-taking, but eventually, it'll pay off in terms of a wealthier lexicon and an capacity to specific subtler thoughts and suppositions more concisely and more elegantly.

3. Teaching about vocabulary

Give a man a fish and you feed him for a day; teach a man to fish and you feed him for a lifetime. [3]

You'll have listened this saying. A comparative guideline can be connected to progressed lexicon instructing in that as an educator with constrained course time, there are as it were so numerous individual words and expressions you'll cover in course. In any case, by instructing learners approximately how English lexicon works, you arm them with aptitudes they can apply past the classroom to assist them

develop their lexicon for themselves. That will, of course, involve teaching lexicon abilities and how to utilize an extend of dialect reference assets. It'll too incorporate looking at word arrangement and commonplace designs of utilization, and raising mindfulness of highlights of lexicon such as enroll, implication, colligation, lexicogrammar, collocation, territorial variety, representation ... the list goes on as the level goes up.

4. Usage is everything

Learning vocabulary is about more than just associating form (spelling and pronunciation) with meaning (denotation). It's equally important to understand when and how it's appropriate to use a word or expression in context. This is true at all levels, but as learners go beyond the most frequent vocabulary, which is often fairly neutral in tone, understanding usage becomes more and more significant. When we meet someone with only a basic command of English, we tend to make allowances; we ignore any slightly odd word choices and try to interpret their general message. When an apparently more fluent speaker makes an unexpected choice of wording though, we're more likely to hesitate over it, to question their intent or to let it colour our impression of them. For example, the use of overly formal word choices might give the impression of someone who's pompous, distant or unfriendly. Conversely, an overly informal tone might come across as disrespectful, immature or patronising. Depth of vocabulary knowledge – understanding exactly how and when a word is used – then becomes as important as simply adding new items to your mental lexicon. [4]

I investigate these four angles of instructing lexicon at progressed levels assist and see at a few down to earth ways able to address them within the ELT classroom.
Rationale of the lesson

We accept that the Lexical Approach has much to offer within the area of lexicon instructing, and thus we have attempted to arrange a lesson that's based on its primary concepts, extraordinarily investigating the utilize of collocations.

GROUP WORK

Working in groups help fostering learning independence, and specially in vocabulary work, learners can exchange knowledge, asking others to explain unknown items. [5]

We also hope that bunch work will be a persuading figure, as students conversation almost places they have been on occasion to, attempting to keep in mind subtle elements together, trading impressions and indeed great recollections!

Synonyms and antonyms

Using synonyms and antonyms is another way of grouping words. It can also be very useful to record synonyms together so that when you are writing or speaking you are able to use a variety of language and not just the same word again and again. There is a tendency for some words to be overused in English. A good example of this is the word nice, which is used to describe so many things that it has become almost bland and non-committal. [6]

In conclusion, These thoughts are in no way thorough. A few of the methods and exercises I utilize more habitually than others and a few I don't utilize at all – generally since I don't think they are suitable for my style of teaching or my students' needs. Finding the leading ways to instruct and learn lexicon along with your students is one of the foremost vital things as a instructor you'll be able do, and having a extend of methods and exercises helps this handle. We know how imperative lexicon is in regard to learning a dialect, but how do we go almost instructing and learning it? In this article we take a see at a number of strategies planned to assist instruct and learn lexicon.

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